

EFFECT OF EDUCATIONAL NURSING INTERVENTION ON FUNCTIONAL MOBILITY AND QUALITY OF LIFE AMONG ELDERLY PATIENTS WITH PARKINSON'S DISEASE

EBRAHIM AHMED ELSAMAHY

Assistant Lecturer, Gerontological Nursing, Faculty of Nursing, Cairo University Egypt.

SOHIER ALI BADR ELDIN

Professor, Gerontological Nursing, Faculty of Nursing, Cairo University Egypt.

EBTESAM MO'AWAD EL-SAYED EBIED

Professor, Gerontological Nursing, Faculty of Nursing Cairo University Egypt.

Abstract

Background: Parkinson's disease (PD) is a progressive neurodegenerative disorder affecting functional mobility and quality of life (QoL) in elderly patients. Educational nursing interventions may help manage symptoms and improve outcomes. **Objective:** To evaluate the effect of an educational nursing intervention on functional mobility and QoL among elderly patients with PD. **Methods:** A quasi-experimental design was used. The study included 60 elderly patients with PD, randomly assigned to either an intervention group (n=30) or a control group (n=30). The intervention group received a 7-session educational program focusing on PD management, including exercises and daily living activities. Pre, post and follow up intervention assessments were conducted using the Parkinson's disease Questionnaire (PDQ-39) and short physical battery scale (to assess functional mobility) **Results:** the mean age of elderly patients with PD was 64.2±1.1 year. The intervention group showed significant improvements in functional mobility and QoL as compared to the control group. The mean scores for FMS and PDQ-39 improved significantly post-intervention ($p<0.05$). **Conclusion:** The educational nursing intervention significantly enhanced functional mobility and QoL in elderly patients with PD. Such interventions should be integrated into the routine care of PD patients to optimize outcomes.

Keywords: Parkinson's Disease, Educational nursing intervention, Functional Mobility, Quality of Life, Nursing.

BACKGROUND

Parkinson's disease (PD) is a progressive neurodegenerative disorder characterized by motor symptoms such as tremor, rigidity, bradykinesia, and postural instability, as well as non-motor symptoms including cognitive impairment, mood disorders, and autonomic dysfunction (Berger et al., 2022). PD is the second most common neurodegenerative disease after Alzheimer's disease, affecting approximately 1% of the population over the age of 60 (Bouça-Machado et al., 2018). The prevalence of PD is expected to increase as the global population ages, making it a significant public health concern (Lee et al., 2021). The impact of PD on functional mobility and quality of life (QoL) is profound. Functional mobility, defined as the ability to move independently and safely in various environments to perform activities of daily living (ADL), is significantly impaired in individuals with PD (Ernst et al., 2023). This impairment increases the risk of falls, loss of independence, and institutionalization. QoL, encompassing physical, psychological,

social, and environmental domains, is also adversely affected by PD, with patients experiencing a decline in physical function, emotional well-being, social participation, and overall life satisfaction (Goetz et al., 2020)

Management of PD typically involves pharmacological treatments aimed at increasing dopamine levels or copying its effects. Levodopa, a precursor of dopamine, is the most effective medication for improving motor symptoms (Thach et al., 2021). However, long-term use of levodopa can lead to motor complications such as dyskinesia and motor fluctuations. Other pharmacological treatments include dopamine agonists, monoamine oxidase B (MAO-B) inhibitors, and catechol-O-methyltransferase (COMT) inhibitors (Berger et al., 2022). Despite the efficacy of pharmacological treatments, non-pharmacological interventions are increasingly recognized as essential components of comprehensive PD management. These interventions include physical therapy, occupational therapy, speech therapy, and educational programs aimed at enhancing self-management skills and improving QoL (Guerra et al., 2023). Educational nursing interventions play a crucial role in empowering patients to manage their condition, adhere to treatment regimens, and engage in beneficial activities such as exercise (Aragon & Kings, 2019). The concept of self-management is integral to chronic disease management, emphasizing the active participation of patients in their own care. In the context of PD, self-care activities may include medication management, regular exercise, dietary modifications, and strategies to cope with motor and non-motor symptoms (Hatano et al., 2022).

Educational nursing interventions for PD patients should encompass both theoretical and practical components. The theoretical component involves providing knowledge about the disease, its progression, and available treatments. The practical component focuses on equipping patients with skills to perform specific exercises and activities that can help manage symptoms and maintain functional mobility. Exercises tailored for PD patients may include balance training, gait training, strength training, and stretching exercises (Stožek et al., 2018). These exercises are designed to improve motor function, reduce rigidity, enhance postural stability, and prevent falls (Prell et al., 2020). Research has shown that educational nursing interventions can significantly improve knowledge, functional mobility, and QoL in patients with chronic conditions, including PD. For example, a study by (Ernst et al., 2023) found that a structured exercise program combined with patient education led to significant improvements in balance, gait, and overall physical functional mobility in PD patients. Another study by Bouça-Machado et al. (2018) demonstrated that educational programs focusing on self-management skills improved adherence to exercise regimens and enhanced QoL in PD patients. In conclusion, PD is a chronic debilitating progressive neurodegenerative disorder condition that significantly impairs functional mobility and QoL in elderly individuals. While pharmacological treatments are essential for managing motor symptoms, educational nursing interventions play a crucial role in empowering patients to take an active role in their care. This study aims to evaluate the effectiveness of an educational nursing intervention in achieving these outcomes among elderly PD patients in Egypt, contributing to the evidence base for non-pharmacological management strategies in this population.

Significance of the Study

As the global population ages, the prevalence of PD is expected to rise, presenting a substantial public health challenge (Bloem et al., 2021). Despite advances in pharmacological treatments, these alone are often insufficient in managing the multifaceted symptoms of PD, necessitating the incorporation of non-pharmacological interventions such as educational programs. In Egypt, the burden of PD is increasing as the population ages. The number of elderly individuals in Egypt is projected to rise from 5.8 million in 2011 to 11.6 million in 2030 (Central Agency for Public Mobilization and Statistics(Osman et al., 2016). This demographic shift underscores the need for effective interventions to manage chronic diseases such as PD. However, there is a scarcity of research on the effectiveness of educational nursing interventions for PD patients in Egypt. This study aims to fill this gap by evaluating the impact of a structured educational nursing intervention on functional mobility and QoL among elderly patients with PD in Egypt. Educational nursing interventions are essential in empowering patients with PD to manage their condition effectively. By enhancing patients' knowledge about the disease, promoting self-management skills, and encouraging adherence to therapeutic regimens, these interventions can lead to improved functional mobility and QoL (Aragon & Kings, 2019)The current study is particularly significant as it seeks to evaluate the impact of a structured educational nursing intervention on elderly patients with PD in Egypt, a region where research on such interventions is limited.

Aim of the Study

To evaluate the effect of an educational nursing intervention on functional mobility and quality of life among elderly patients with Parkinson's disease.

Research Hypothesis

To achieve the aim of the study, the following hypotheses have been formulated:

- 1) Elderly patients with Parkinson's disease who was receive the proposed educational nursing intervention (study group) was exhibit higher functional mobility mean score in the post test than in pretest mean sore and higher mean score than the control group.
- 2) Elderly patients with Parkinson's disease who was receive the proposed educational nursing intervention (study group) was exhibit higher quality of life mean score in the post test than in the pretest and higher mean score than the control group.

METHODS

Study Design

This study employed a quasi-experimental design with pre-test and post-test control groups to evaluate the effect of an educational nursing intervention on functional mobility and quality of life (QoL) among elderly patients with Parkinson's disease (PD).

Setting

The current study was conducted in neurology outpatient clinics at Kaser Eleni teaching hospital which is one of the university hospitals affiliated to Cairo University. In outpatient the assigned doctor examine the patient physically using standard tools to exclude other diseases (Hoehn and Yahr scale to specify the severity of the disease) and short physical performance battery scale, after that the doctor confirm PD diagnosis the medical management was written for the patient. PD patients follow up every month.

Study sample and sampling technique.

Purposive sampling of elderly patients aged from 60 years and more who diagnosed as PD patients, with stage from 1 to 3 on Hoehn and Yahr scale was recruited for the current study from the outpatients of the neurology clinics. Participants were selected using purposive sampling and were randomly assigned to either the intervention group (n=30) or the control group (n=30) using a computer-generated randomization sequence. Randomization ensured that both groups were comparable in terms of demographic and clinical characteristics. The intervention group received the educational nursing intervention, and the control group received the standard routine care in the hospital outpatient clinics. Half of the elderly patient with Parkinson's was allocated the intervention group (even number) and the other half of the elderly patient with Parkinson's was the control group (odd numbers). Both groups have the same environment based on the initial assessment done by the researcher, and the elderly patient have similar characteristics. Data was collected over a period of 3 months.

Intervention

Procedure for Data Collection

Official permissions to carry out the research were obtained from the Research Ethics Committee at Faculty of Nursing- Cairo University. Also, an official permission was obtained from hospital administrators before the beginning of the study; the researcher explained the purpose of the study was explained. Elderly patient with PD were assured that they have the right to withdraw from the study at any time. Then, written consent was obtained from each patient who accepted to participate in the study. Anonymity and confidentiality were also secured. The study was conducted in the following phases: assessment, planning, implementation, and evaluation.

1- Assessment phase:

The elderly were assessed using Tool I:

Tool I: The elderly patient's demographic questionnaire.

Tool II: Modified Hoehn and Yahr Scale to describe how motor symptoms progress in PD Rating symptoms on a scale of 1 to 5, while the tool III Short Functional Mobility battery was used to assess functional mobility of patient, **and tool IV** Parkinson's Disease Quality of Life Questionnaire (PDQ-39) is used to assess health related quality of life.

The assessment phase was over 7 weeks, the researcher visited the outpatient clinics one day/week from 9 am to 1pm. Each patient interviewed individually and spent 20 - 30 minutes with the researcher and this was done and repeated three as pre, posttest and follow-up.

2- Planning phase:

Based on the results of the assessment phase, the researcher planned the educational nursing intervention to improve elderly patient with PD practices toward Parkinson's, the educational nursing intervention included exercise and advice about daily activities. It was given on an individualized basis and the researcher approached the studied patient weekly for 3 sessions.

3- Implementation phase:

This phase is concerned with the implementation of the educational nursing intervention using individualized teaching sessions (7 sessions), every session contains the theoretical part about PD part and practical part regarding exercises. Each session ranged between 20 to 30 minutes for each patient; the first session was about introduction to patient about the he main aim of the study, the second session was an introduction about the Parkinson's (definition, causes and signs and symptoms), third session was general instructions to the elderly patients about life style modification such as fall prevention. The session also included training about balance and gait exercises that done by the patient under researcher guidance), the fourth session was about methods of treatment, nutrition for elderly with Parkinson's and stretching exercises, the fifth session was about how to deal with complication of PD (constipation) and stretching exercises, the sixth session was about instructions about how to deal with drooling and strengthen exercises, the 7th was conclusion and immediate posttest. Three months later the researcher collects patients' research retaining data to assess the effect of the educational nursing intervention. All sessions were implemented at the outpatient clinic, using group discussion, demonstration approaches, audiovisual aids such as booklet, posters, and video film about exercise to facilitate the process of health education, adding to those each elderly individually received a copy of the booklet of the educational nursing intervention guidelines.

4- Evaluation phase:

The researcher assessed the effect of educational nursing intervention on functional mobility and Parkinson's disease related quality of life using the tool II: modified Hoehn and Yahr scale, Tool III: short functional mobility battery and tool VI Parkinson's disease quality of life questionnaire (PDQ-39). Evaluation was performed immediately and three months after implementing the educational nursing intervention.

Data Collection

Data Collection Tools

Data was collected using four tools:

Tool I: Demographic questionnaire

The elderly's demographic questionnaire includes the demographic characteristics of elderly as age, gender, level of education, previous occupation, and current occupation, past and current medical history.

Tool II: Short physical performance battery (SPPB)

It was developed by the National Institute on Aging (NIA). Three domains, which include balance, usual or self-selected gait speed, and lower limb strength, are assessed by a three-stage balance test (feet side-by-side, semi tandem, and tandem positions), a 3-m or 4-m gait speed test (time spent to walk the course), and a repetitive chair stand test (five times chair sit-to-stand test), respectively. A 0- to 12-point scale is used to score the sum of the three assessments with higher point values corresponding with greater levels of physical function and lower disability, whereas lower point values correspond with lower levels of physical function and higher disability, respectively. The SPPB is used to assess functional performance, functional mobility, balance, and lower extremity strength in older adults (3–6). This test requires minimal equipment and can be performed by health-fitness professionals that work with elderly clients in field, community, or clinical settings. The SPPB has demonstrated sensitivity and responsiveness to exercise-based interventions over time (4–7) and can be completed in approximately 10 to 15 minutes. Results from the SPPB can help health-fitness professionals formulate physical activity and exercise program interventions to improve physical function in their older adult clients. Because it has demonstrated good sensitivity to changes in physical condition and performance over time, it can help guide program design and monitor improvements in fitness and lower limb function upon reassessment (Ronai & Gallo, 2019).

Tool III Parkinson's Disease Quality of Life Questionnaire (PDQ-39)

The PDQ-39 comprises 39 questions with five different options of answer related to the frequency of the disease manifestation. The answers refer to the impact of the illness on the patient's life in the previous month, as explained before the interview. The 39 questions are divided into 8 dimensions: mobility (10 questions), activities of daily living (ADL) (6), emotional well-being (6), stigma (4), social support (3), cognition (4), communication (3), and bodily discomfort (3). The score for each question ranges from zero (0) to four (4): "never" =0; "occasionally" =1; "sometimes" =2; "often" = 3; "always" =4. The final score is the result of the following equation: the sum of each question score divided by the result times 4 (the maximal score for each question), divided by the total number of questions. This result is multiplied times by 100. Each dimension score ranges from 0 to 100 in a linear scale, in which zero is the best and 100 the worst quality of life (Opara et al., 2018). This tool was collected by the researcher due to the disease limitation and short attention span of PD elderly patients.

Data Analysis

Data were analyzed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 26 Descriptive statistics (mean, standard deviation, frequency, and percentage) were

used to summarize demographic and clinical characteristics. Inferential statistics were used to test the hypotheses: Independent t-tests, Paired t-tests and Repeated Measures ANOVA

Ethical Considerations

Written approval received from the Committee of Scientific Research Ethics at the Faculty of Nursing, Cairo-University. In addition, official permission to conduct the proposed study was obtained from the Faculty of Nursing- Cairo University. Written informed consents were obtained from the elderly after explaining the aim of the study, its benefits, and risks, the duration of the study and the data collection tools. The researcher informed the elderly that all data gathered during the study was confidential and they have the right to withdraw from the study at any time without giving any reason. Besides, the elderly were informed that data was used for the purpose of this study, and it was not reused in other studies except with permission.

RESULTS

Part I: Demographic characteristics (personal) and the medical history between control and study groups of elderly patients with Parkinson’s diseases (tables: 1-2).

Table (1): Distribution of personal data between control and study groups of elderly (n=60).

Personal data	Categories	Control group (n=30)		Study group (n==30)		Chi square test	
		No.	%	No.	%	χ^2	P
Age	60< 65 years	23	76.7	23	76.7	.31	.86
	65< 70 years	4	13.3	5	16.7		
	70< 75 years	3	10	2	6.7		
	Mean \pmSD	64.2 \pm 1.10		64.26 \pm 1.11			
Employment status-	Employee	5	16.7	3	10	6.5	0.162
	Framer	1	3.3	5	16.7		
	Craftsman	4	13.3	5	16.7		
	Un employed	5	16.7	5	16.7		
	Retired	15	50	8	26.7		
Income	Sufficient	17	56.7	20	66.7	0.635	0.426
	Sufficient	13	43.3	10	33.3		
Type of residence	Rented	12	40	14	46.7	10.0	0.21
	Owned	18	60	16	53.3		
With whom elderly live?	Alone	2	23.3	0	0	11.19	0.11
	With wife/husband	11	36.7	12	40		
	With sones	12	40	14	46.7		
	With wife/husband and sones	0	0	4	13.3		

P value is significant at ≤ 0.05 , highly significant at ≤ 0.001 .

Table (1) denotes that there were insignificant statistical differences ($p>0.05$) in personal data, (age group, Employment status, Income, type of residence, and with whom elderly live) between control and study groups which means that the two groups are comparable and homogeneous groups. Concerning the age of the elderly, 76.7% of elderly in the control group aged 60-65 years, furthermore 76.7 % in the study group aged 60-65 years with a mean of 64.2 ± 1.1 years in the control and 64.26 in the study groups. Concerning the income, 56.7% of elderly in the control group described their income as sufficient to 66.7% in study group. In terms type of residence, 60% of the elderly in the control group homes were owned to 53.3 % in the study group. Regarding with whom elderly live, 40 % of the elderly in the control group live with sons and 46 % of them in the study group also live with sons.

Figure 1: Distribution of elderly patients regarding marital status (n=60)

Figure (1) reveals that 73.3%, and 26.7% in the control group were married and widowed respectively compared to 3.3%, 76.6%, and 20% in the study group were divorced, married, widowed respectively.

Figure 2: Distribution of elderly patients regarding sex (n=60)

Figure (2) shows that, 73.3%, and 26.7% in the control group were male and female respectively compared to 86.7% and 13.3% in the study group respectively.

Figure 3: Distribution of elderly patients regarding income sources (n=60)

Figure (3) indicates that 20%, 33.3%, and 46.7% in the control group elderly income sources were from work, pension, and sones respectively compared to 23.3%, 40% and 36.7% in the study group respectively.

Figure 4: Percentage distribution of elderly patients regarding educational level (n=60)

Figure (4) reveals that, 13.3%, 6.7.3%,10%,46.7 and 23.3%of elderly in the control group were cannot read or write ,primary education , preparatory education, secondary education and university education respectively compared to 13.3%,6,7%,16.7%.40%, and 20% in the study group respectively.

Table 2: Distribution of the Elderly patients regarding Medical History (n=60).

Medical history	Categories	Control group (n=30)		Study group (n=30)		Chi square test	
		No.	%	No.	%	χ^2	P
Chronic illness	Yes	24	80	22	73.3	17.14	.09
	No	6	20	8	26.7		
History of stroke	Yes	10	33.3	5	16.7	2.22	.14
	No	20	66.7	25	83.3		
Family history of PD	Yes	2	6.7	4	13.3	.74	.39
	No	28	93.3	26	86.7		

P value is significant at ≤ 0.05 , highly significant at ≤ 0.001 .

Table (2) reveals that there were insignificant statistical differences $p > 0.05$ in medical history between control and study groups which means that the two groups are homogenous groups. Also, it shows that 80 % of the elderly in control group complained of at least one chronic illness, while 73.3 % in study group complained of at least one chronic illness. Regarding history of stroke, 66.7% of elderly in control group and 83.3% of elderly in study group have no history of stroke. Concerning family history of PD, table shows that 93.3% of elderly in control group don't have family history of PD compared to 86.7% in the study group.

Table (3): comparing of mean total functional mobility scores of the elderly patient in control and study groups of elderly patients in pre, post, and follow up test (n=60)

Functional mobility	Control group (n=30)								Study group (n=30)							
	Pretest		Posttest		Follow up			Repeated measures ANOVA	Pretest		Posttest		Follow up		Repeated measures ANOVA	
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	F		P	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean		SD
Total equilibrium points	3.4	0.72	3.42	0.72	3.32	.61	0.9	0.89	2.46	0.81	3.01	0.86	3	0.86	0.06	0.04
Total walking points	1.7	0.43	1.61	0.47	1.70	.40	0.72	0.79	1.31	0	3.14	0.37	3.1	0.37	2.90	0.01
Total standing points	1.7	0.53	1.8	0.52	1.85	.45	1.06	0.86	1.23	0.43	2.78	0.85	1.76	0.85	5.15	0.01
Total functional mobility scores	6.8	1.68	6.83	1.71	6.87	1.46	2.68	0.54	5	1.24	8.93	2.08	7.86	2.08	8.35	0.00

P value is significant at ≤ 0.05 , highly significant at ≤ 0.001 .

Table (3) indicates that there were insignificant statistical differences ($p>0.05$) in short physical performance battery score for all dimensions and total scores among control group.

While there were significant statistical differences ($p\leq 0.05$) in physical performance scores for all dimensions and total scores among the study group

Table (4): comparing of total mean functional mobility among elderly patients with Parkinson’s disease in

Functional mobility of elderly	Pretest						Posttest						Follow up					
	Control group (n=30)		Study group. (n=30)		Independent t test		Control group. (n=30)		Study group. (n=30)		Independent t test		Control group. (n=30)		Study group. (n=30)		Independent t test	
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	t	p	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	t	p	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	t	p
Total equilibrium	3.4	0.72	2.46	0.81	23.34	0.43	3.42	0.72	3.01	0.86	19.01	0.00	3.32	.61	3	0.86	0.16	0.01
Total walking points	1.7	0.43	1.31	0	95.29	0.56	1.61	0.47	3.14	0.37	32.85	0.00	1.70	.40	3.1	0.37	2.21	0.01
Total standing points	1.7	0.53	1.23	0.43	13.86	0.31	1.8	0.52	2.78	0.85	0.13	0.02	1.85	.45	1.76	0.85	5.15	0.01
Total functional mobility score	6.8	1.68	5	1.24	93.57	0.09	6.83	1.71	8.93	2.08	37.10	0.00	6.87	1.46	7.86	2.08	8.35	0.00

pre, post, and follow up between control and study groups (n=60).

P value is significant at ≤ 0.05 , highly significant at ≤ 0.001 .

Table (4) shows that there were insignificant statistical differences ($p>0.05$) in all items of functional mobility between control and study groups at pretest. While there were significant statistical differences ($p\leq 0.05$) in all items of functional mobility between control and study groups at posttest point.

Table (5): comparing total mean parkinsonism disease quality of life dimension scores in control and study groups among elderly patients during pretest, posttest and follow up(n=60).

Dimension of PDQOL	Control group(n=30)								Study group(n=30)							
	Pretest		Posttest		Follow up		Repeated measures ANOVA		Pretest		Posttest		Follow up		Repeated measures ANOVA	
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	F	P	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	F	P
Mobility	22.67	1.68	23.9	1.68	12.86	0.35	1.21	0.82	23.53	2.5	29.96	1.83	29.26	2.59	25.63	0.00
Activity of daily living (ADL)	12.5	1.1	12.9	0.9	11.87	0.35	0.9	0.76	14.1	1.64	20.4	2.1	19.06	1.65	26.48	0.00
Emotional well-being	13.8	0.81	13.1	0.79	12.83	0.38	0.93	0.57	13.28	2.22	19.2	2.1	17.3	1.62	9.51	0.00
Social support	4.2	0.86	4.26	0.98	4.43	0.63	0.08	0.78	5.1	0.99	8.83	0.94	8.06	1.5	22.80	0.00
Cognition	6.03	1.3	6.43	1.12	6.40	0.62	0.9	0.78	5.9	1.15	10.5	1.25	9.2	1.42	33.30	0.00
Communication	4.3	1.51	4.31	1.49	4.57	0.50	0.01	0.93	3.16	1.2	8.03	0.61	7.2	0.94	30.19	0.00
Body discomfort	5.06	1.11	5.06	1.11	5.12	0.98	0.0	1.0	4.83	1.44	8.1	0.8	7.1	0.8	4.80	0.01
Total PDQOL	68.56	8.37	69.96	8.07	58.08	3.80	4.03	5.64	69.9	11.14	105.02	9.63	97.18	10.52	66.26	0.00

P value is significant at ≤ 0.05 , highly significant at ≤ 0.001 .

Table (5) exposes that there were insignificant statistical differences ($p > 0.05$) in mean total parkinsonism disease quality of life scores for all dimensions of PQOL and total scores among control group. While there were highly significant statistical differences ($p \leq 0.05$) in mean total Parkinsonism disease quality of life scores for all dimensions of PQOL and total scores among study group.

Table (6): Comparing total parkinsonism disease quality of life mean scores in disease in pre, post, and follow up between control and study groups (n=60).

PDQOL	Pretest						Posttest						Follow up					
	Control group (n=30)		Study group (n=30)		Independent t test		Control group (n=30)		Study group (n=30)		Independent t test		Control group (n=30)		Study group (n=30)		Independent t test	
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	t	p	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	t	p	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	t	P
Mobility	22.67	1.68	23.53	2.5	60.95	0.16	23.9	1.68	29.96	1.83	158.11	0.00	12.86	0.35	29.26	2.59	22.63	0.00
ADL	12.5	1.1	14.1	1.64	168.14	0.81	12.9	0.9	20.4	2.1	2.13	0.00	11.87	0.35	19.06	1.65	21.38	0.00
Emotional	13.8	0.81	13.28	2.22	205.35	0.42	13.1	0.79	19.2	2.1	97.53	0.00	12.83	0.38	17.3	1.62	9.21	0.00
Social support	4.2	0.86	5.1	0.99	14.24	0.36	4.26	0.98	8.83	0.94	3.02	0.00	4.43	0.63	8.06	1.5	20.80	0.00
Cognition	6.03	1.3	5.9	1.15	0.17	0.68	6.43	1.12	10.5	1.25	19.42	0.00	6.40	0.62	9.2	1.42	13.30	0.00
Communication	4.3	1.51	3.16	1.2	10.30	0.90	4.31	1.49	8.03	0.61	60.85	0.00	4.57	0.50	7.2	0.94	31.19	0.00
Body discomfort	5.06	1.11	4.83	1.44	94.71	0.51	5.06	1.11	8.1	0.8	250.86	0.00	5.12	0.98	7.1	0.8	41.80	0.01
Total PDQOL	68.56	8.37	69.9	11.14	99.15	0.65	69.96	8.07	105.02	9.63	367.78	0.00	58.08	3.80	97.18	10.52	69.26	0.00

P value is significant at ≤ 0.05 , highly significant at ≤ 0.001

Table (6) produces that there were insignificant statistical differences ($p > 0.05$) total Parkinsonism disease quality of life scores between control and study groups at pretest. While there were highly significant statistical differences ($p \leq 0.05$) in all items of total Parkinsonism disease quality of life scores between control and study groups at posttest and also at follow up test.

DISCUSSION

The findings of this study demonstrate the significant impact of an educational nursing intervention on functional mobility and quality of life (QoL) among elderly patients with Parkinson's disease (PD). The intervention led to improvements in functional mobility, and QoL, highlighting the importance of comprehensive educational nursing intervention in managing chronic neurodegenerative diseases like PD.

Concerning elderly personal data, the current study showed that there were insignificant statistical differences ($p > 0.05$) in all personal data (Age group, Employment status, Income, Type of residence) between control and study groups which means that the two groups are comparable groups due to random assignment of the two group (study and control group). Concerning the mean age of the elderly patients the current study showed that it was sixty four, which aligned with the study that done by (Isernia et al., 2020) to identify the effects of an innovative telerehabilitation intervention for people with Parkinson's disease on quality of life, motor, and non-motor abilities with sample size sixty three participant showed that the mean age is sixty six year .

Regarding marital status the current study revealed that about two third of elderly patient with Parkinson's disease were married this aligned with (Bock et al., 2024) who conducted a study on twenty-eight elderly patient to describe elderly patient and care partner experiences with a novel, community-based palliative care intervention for Parkinson's disease and found that about two third of elderly patients were married.

According to the study's findings more than two third of elderly patients were male in study and control group. This result is consistent with (Choi et al., 2020) who studied two hundred and seven PD elderly patients' uncertainty-related variables, economic status, disease severity, social support, and resilience on uncertainty in people with PD. And analyzed direct and indirect paths between these variables. The findings of this study reported the development interventions to help people with PD in coping effectively with disease, the data was collected from two neurology out elderly patient departments of a tertiary hospital from two cities, Seoul and Gyeonggi, and meetings of Korean Parkinson Disease Association.

According to the current study's findings, more than one third of elderly patients in the study and control group have passed secondary education. This result somewhat not matched with the result of the study done by (Hellqvist et al., 2020) to identify the effect of Self-management education for elderly with Parkinson's disease and their care partners one hundred and seven Sweden participant, and founded that more than one third of study and control group elderly completed university education. From researchers' point of view, it may be due to economic status of elderly patients in Sweden compared to Egypt (low-income country) From the current researcher's point of view these findings may be explained by the fact that the elderly in the current study had fewer opportunities for education in the past especially in the developing countries which impacted the elderly knowledge about health promotion and healthy lifestyle.

Regarding chronic illness such as DM and HTN, around three-quarters of older people in both groups complain of at least one chronic disease. These findings are aligned with the study done by (Patel et al., 2023) on one hundred and ten elderly patient to examines the prevalence, patterns, and correlates of psychiatric comorbidity and multimorbidity among in-elderly patients hospitalized with PD/APS (atypical parkinsonian syndromes). Depression was the most common, followed by any anxiety disorder and psychotic disorders. The prevalence rates of depression forty seven percent and anxiety disorders thirty five percent among PD elderly patients.

In terms of history of stroke, the current study showed that around one third of control group and less than one third of study group had history of stroke. these result is congruent with the study done by (Kummer et al., 2019) to examine the Associations between cerebrovascular risk factors and Parkinson disease and founded that Among mor than one million Medicare beneficiaries followed for a mean of five years, fifteen thousand five hundred thirty-one elderly (1.5%) participants were diagnosed with Parkinson disease and eighty-one thousand nine hundred seventy-four (7.9%) were diagnosed with Alzheimer disease. The researcher concluded that cerebrovascular risk factors were associated with the subsequent diagnosis of Parkinson disease. From researcher point of view this result may be explained as the risk factors of stroke have significant impact on brain vascularity and blood supply to brain cells leading to impairing main brain function and normal hormonal physiology. Particularly, dopamine levels and function can be affected by stroke. Dopamine is a neurotransmitter involved in movement, motivation, and reward. Stroke damage in certain areas can lead to dopamine imbalances, contributing to movement disorders like Parkinson's disease.

Regarding family history of PD, the current study revealed that low prevalence of family history of PD among elderly patients with PD. These findings are not consistent with (Jacobs et al., 2020) who studied One Thousand Two Hundred Seventy PD elderly patient in UK to identify Parkinson's disease determinants, reported that Strong evidence of association between PD and a positive family history of PD, a positive family history of dementia was also founded. From a researcher's point of view this contradiction may be due to the small sample size in the current study, so further research needed to be conducted on large sample size.

Additionally large case-control study assessing thirty-one protective/risk factors of PD, including environmental and lifestyle factors, comorbid conditions, and drugs. The study enrolled Six Hundred Ninety Four elderly with PD and six hundred forty healthy controls from six neurologic centers that done by (Belvisi et al., 2020) showed that only coffee consumption, smoking, physical activity, family history of PD, acid stomach, and exposure to pesticides, oils, metals, and general anesthesia, were independently associated with PD.

The current study's findings revealed that mor than one third of elderly patient with PD live with one of family members who may be one sons, wife, husband. these result is in the same line with (Hellqvist et al., 2020) whose research was about self-management education for persons with Parkinson's and their partners on one hundred seven PD

elderly patients and reported that more than two thirds of elderly live with one family member that may be sons or wife. From the researcher's point of view, the fact that one third of elderly patients with Parkinson's disease is living with one or more family member due to the nature of extended family that provided with the study sample. Living with a family member may provide support and assistance in managing the challenges associated with PD.

Regarding functional mobility, the current study indicates that there were insignificant statistical differences in short physical performance battery score (functional mobility) for all dimensions and total scores among control group. While there were significant statistical differences in physical battery scores for all dimensions (equilibrium, walking and standing) and total scores among study group that is mean improvement in functional mobility among study group. These results go on the same line with the result of the study done by (Vieira de Moraes Filho et al., 2020) on 62 PD elderly patient to investigate the effect of Progressive Resistance Training on Bradykinesia, Motor Symptoms(tremor, rigidity ,slowness of movement) and Functional Performance in Elderly patients with Parkinson's Disease .The study highlights that there was improvements in the disease motor symptoms with a few weeks of intervention. The significant effects on bradykinesia, without an increase in muscle strength, suggest that the intervention promoted neural enhancements in a short-term, to improve the functional performance of trained individuals.

Regarding equilibrium, the current study showed that there were significant statistical differences in total equilibrium scores among study groups after application of educational program and exercise for PD elderly patient. These results are in line with the study done by(Ernst et al., 2023)on Sixty Four PD elderly patient to assess the effects of the rehabilitation program on balance, gait, motor performance and trunk rotations in PD elderly patients, and the author concluded that The rehabilitation group significantly improved in balance and gait outcomes, timed activities and trunk rotations both in comparison to the control group and baseline results.

Regarding walking point the current study showed that there were significant statistical differences in total walking point scores among study group after application of educational program and exercise for PD elderly patient. These results is in the same line with the result from meta-analysis for RCT trails that done by (Shen et al., 2018) using twenty five randomized control trials RCT trails to assess Effects of Exercise on Falls, Balance, and Gait Ability in Parkinson's Diseases and report positive balance and gait outcomes, meta-analysis is the first to report that exercise training could decrease the fall rates of PD participants by about sixty percent over both the short- and long-terms..

Regarding total standing score, the current study showed that there were significant statistical differences in total standing scores among study group after application of educational program and exercise for PD elderly patient. These result is in the line with the study that done by (Bouça-Machado et al., 2020) to investigate outcome measures for evaluating the effect of a multidisciplinary intervention on axial symptoms of

Parkinson's disease on twenty two patients in Portugal , and concluded that there were improvement in standing and walking score after intervention

Regarding functional mobility, the current study showed that there were significant statistical differences in all items of functional mobility between control and study groups at the posttest point. This result is in the line with (Barbalho et al., 2019) who conducted study To evaluate the effects of low-volume resistance training on the physical and functional capacity of older patients with Parkinson's disease, on fifty four elderly patient with Parkinson's disease. The author concluded that there is great improvement in total functional mobility of elderly patients with PD.

Regarding quality of life the current study showed there were insignificant statistical differences in mean total Parkinsonism disease quality of life scores for all dimensions and total scores among control group. While there were significant statistical differences in mean total Parkinsonism disease quality of life scores for all dimensions and total scores among study group after intervention. These findings completely matched with the results of the study systematic review and meta-analysis about Effect of Exercise on Quality of Life in Parkinson's Disease that done by (Chen et al., 2020) concluded that Exercise interventions, especially aerobic exercise, dance, and Tai Chi, significantly improve QOL in PD elderly patients.

The current study showed that there was significant statistical difference between study and control group regarding movement and activity of daily living after application of educational nursing intervention ,these results go in the same line with the study done by (Isernia et al., 2020)to investigate Effects of an Innovative Telerehabilitation Intervention for People With Parkinson's Disease on Quality of Life, Motor, and Non-motor Abilities and concluded that The digital health elderly patient-tailored rehabilitation program resulted in improving motor and non-motor abilities and quality of life in clinical setting, enhancing the motor function in telerehabilitation at home, and maintaining the non-motor abilities and quality of life at follow-up. Soon, people with PD can be supported also at home with individualized rehabilitation strategies for a better quality of life and wellbeing along with lower costs for society.

In conclusion, our study contributes valuable insights into the benefits of educational nursing interventions for PD elderly patients, emphasizing the need for comprehensive, multidisciplinary approaches to care. Future research should focus on identifying the most effective strategies for delivering elderly patient education, considering the diverse needs of the PD population. By refining these interventions, healthcare providers can better support the physical, psychological, and informational well-being of PD elderly patients, leading to improved quality of life and more positive disease outcomes.

Implications for Practice

The findings of this study have several important implications for clinical practice and healthcare policy. First, they highlight the critical role of educational nursing interventions in the comprehensive management of PD. Healthcare providers should consider integrating structured educational programs into routine care for PD patients to improve

knowledge, functional mobility, and QoL. Second, the study underscores the importance of multidisciplinary approaches that combine pharmacological treatments with non-pharmacological interventions such as exercise and education (Connolly & Lang, 2014). This holistic approach can address the multifaceted needs of PD patients more effectively than pharmacological treatments alone.

Third, the positive outcomes observed in this study suggest that similar educational nursing interventions could be beneficial for managing other chronic diseases. As the population ages and the prevalence of chronic conditions increases, healthcare systems must adapt by incorporating comprehensive, patient-centered approaches to disease management (Dorsey et al., 2018). Educational programs that enhance patients' self-care capabilities can reduce the burden on healthcare systems by improving disease outcomes and reducing the need for hospitalization and institutional care (Fox et al., 2012).

Limitations and Future Research

While this study provides valuable insights, it has several limitations that should be addressed in future research. The sample size was relatively small and limited to a specific geographic area, which may limit the generalizability of the findings. Additionally, the study relied on self-reported measures of QoL and functional mobility, which may be subject to bias. Objective measures and longitudinal follow-up would strengthen the evidence for the long-term benefits of educational nursing interventions.

Moreover, the intervention focused primarily on physical exercises. Future research could explore the integration of other components such as nutritional counseling, cognitive training, and mental health support to provide a more comprehensive approach to PD management. Investigating the cost-effectiveness of such interventions would also be valuable for informing healthcare policy and resource allocation.

Recommendation

Based on current study findings, the following is recommended:

Recommendations for research

1. Conduct further research that includes larger sample size of elderly to generalize the results.

Recommendations for elderly patient with PD

2. Increase awareness campaigns regarding Parkinson's disease.

Recommendations for gerontological nursing practice

3. Implement educational nursing intervention (knowledge and exercise) to manage signs and symptoms of PD and management.
4. Training program for gerontological nurses about PD disease and related nursing care.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this study demonstrated that an educational nursing intervention significantly improves knowledge, functional mobility, and QoL among elderly patients with PD. The findings highlight the importance of integrating educational programs into the comprehensive management of chronic diseases. By empowering patients with knowledge and practical skills, healthcare providers can enhance self-care capabilities, improve health outcomes, and ultimately, improve the quality of life for individuals living with chronic conditions like PD.

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